

Instrument 3 (Assessment)

Name: _____ Date: _____
 Course: _____ Enrollment: _____

Disagree Agree

CONFORMITY

- | | | | | | | | |
|---|---|---|---|---|---|---|---|
| 1. The proposed ERtext solution, with a textual approach, presents conventions compatible with those foreseen for ER modeling. | <table border="1" style="border-collapse: collapse; width: 100px; height: 20px;"> <tr> <td style="width: 16.6%;">1</td> <td style="width: 16.6%;">2</td> <td style="width: 16.6%;">3</td> <td style="width: 16.6%;">4</td> <td style="width: 16.6%;">5</td> <td style="width: 16.6%;">6</td> </tr> </table> | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 | 6 |
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| 2. The brModelo tool, with a graphical approach, presents conventions compatible with those foreseen for ER modeling. | <table border="1" style="border-collapse: collapse; width: 100px; height: 20px;"> <tr> <td style="width: 16.6%;">1</td> <td style="width: 16.6%;">2</td> <td style="width: 16.6%;">3</td> <td style="width: 16.6%;">4</td> <td style="width: 16.6%;">5</td> <td style="width: 16.6%;">6</td> </tr> </table> | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 | 6 |
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UNDERSTANDABILITY

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|--|---|---|---|---|---|---|---|
| 3. The proposed ERtext solution, with a textual approach, is appropriate to perform activities related to the ER modeling approach. | <table border="1" style="border-collapse: collapse; width: 100px; height: 20px;"> <tr> <td style="width: 16.6%;">1</td> <td style="width: 16.6%;">2</td> <td style="width: 16.6%;">3</td> <td style="width: 16.6%;">4</td> <td style="width: 16.6%;">5</td> <td style="width: 16.6%;">6</td> </tr> </table> | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 | 6 |
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LEARNABILITY

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|--|---|---|---|---|---|---|---|
| 5. The proposed ERtext solution, with a textual approach, is easy to understand in use. | <table border="1" style="border-collapse: collapse; width: 100px; height: 20px;"> <tr> <td style="width: 16.6%;">1</td> <td style="width: 16.6%;">2</td> <td style="width: 16.6%;">3</td> <td style="width: 16.6%;">4</td> <td style="width: 16.6%;">5</td> <td style="width: 16.6%;">6</td> </tr> </table> | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 | 6 |
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OPERABILITY

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QUALITY IN USE

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|--|---|---|---|---|---|---|---|
| 9. The proposed ERtext solution, with a textual approach, allows users to achieve the proposed modeling objectives. | <table border="1" style="border-collapse: collapse; width: 100px; height: 20px;"> <tr> <td style="width: 16.6%;">1</td> <td style="width: 16.6%;">2</td> <td style="width: 16.6%;">3</td> <td style="width: 16.6%;">4</td> <td style="width: 16.6%;">5</td> <td style="width: 16.6%;">6</td> </tr> </table> | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 | 6 |
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PRODUCTIVITY

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|---|---|---|---|---|---|---|---|
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SATISFACTION

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| 13. The proposed ERtext solution, with a textual approach, has a satisfactory performance during its use. | <table border="1" style="border-collapse: collapse; width: 100px; height: 20px;"> <tr> <td style="width: 16.6%;">1</td> <td style="width: 16.6%;">2</td> <td style="width: 16.6%;">3</td> <td style="width: 16.6%;">4</td> <td style="width: 16.6%;">5</td> <td style="width: 16.6%;">6</td> </tr> </table> | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 | 6 |
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